

1 **A method based on asymmetric flow field flow fractionation**
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3 **hyphenated to inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry**
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6 **for the monitoring of platinum nanoparticles in water samples**
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21 **Abstract**

22 An analytical methodology based on asymmetric flow field flow fractionation hyphenated
23 to inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (AF4-ICP-MS) has been developed for
24 monitoring citrate coated platinum nanoparticles (PtNPs) of different sizes (5, 30, and 50
25 nm) in water samples. Several factors have been optimized, such as carrier composition,
26 AF4 separation program, focusing step or cross flow values. Under the optimum
27 conditions, PtNPs can be fractionated in about 30 minutes in a single run with quantitative
28 recoveries of the membrane ($100 \pm 7 \%$, n=5). The optimized method has been
29 successfully applied to study transformations, not only in size but also surface
30 modifications, of PtNPs in synthetic and natural water samples over time. The effect of
31 organic matter was specifically studied, and it was found to be a critical parameter. The
32 analytical strategy followed in this work can be very useful to develop further
33 environmental studies involving PtNPs.

38 **Keywords**

39 Platinum nanoparticles; asymmetric flow field flow fractionation; inductively coupled
40 plasma mass spectrometry; water; humic acid; organic matter.

1. Introduction

The use of nanotechnology and nanomaterials in consumer and industrial products has increased rapidly over the last years [1]. Specially, metallic nanoparticles are widely applied due to their unusual physicochemical properties [2] and, among them, platinum nanoparticles (PtNPs) are extensively used in different applications, being one of the most important automotive catalytic converters [3]. Their unique catalytic properties make them very useful for the oxidation of carbon monoxide and hydrocarbons and for the reduction of nitrogen oxides [4]. This catalytic activity is strongly linked to particle size and shape [5].

Mechanical abrasion and chemical reactions at the catalyst surface are responsible for the emission through exhaust gases into the environment of PtNPs, which are expected to be in a size range from <10 nm to 400 nm [6,7]. The annual global platinum emission from vehicle exhaust gases is estimated to be at 0.01 - 6 ton per year, leading to dispersion and accumulation of PtNPs in different environmental compartments [8]. They are emitted and subsequently propagated mainly along roadways [8,9] but might be transported to rivers and lakes through run-off water [10] or taken by plants and organisms [11,12]. Recent studies have shown that platinum in road dust and its leachates was in particulate form, predominantly ranging sizes from 9 to 21 nm [13] but their fate, persistence, and stability in natural systems are still little known. Therefore, there is a need to control the presence of these NPs in the different environmental compartments, study their transfer to living organisms and assess the toxicity they can generate. The development of analytical methodologies for the determination of PtNPs in matrices of environmental interest is required to satisfy all these needs.

The study of NPs is a complex task that has been traditionally focused on physical parameters, such as size (size distribution), shape, state of aggregation or structure. For

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67 this purpose, spectroscopic techniques, such as Fourier transform infrared or Raman, or
68 techniques of electron microscopy (transmission electron and scanning electron
69 microscopy, among others) have been used [14]. However, apart from having limited
70 sensitivity and reproducibility, these techniques very often require that NPs are in dry
71 state rather than in solution to make them suitable for measurement. This sample
72 preparation usually results in induced polydisperse particle size distributions [15] and
73 other unknown alterations in the state of the NPs [16] that considerably reduce sample
74 representativity and prevent these techniques from distinguishing between NPs and ionic
75 forms. Therefore, new analytical tools that are complementary to the existing ones are
76 required to tackle this issue, and important developments have been proposed recently.
77 One of the new options is single particle inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry
78 (sp-ICP-MS). This technique provides information concerning NP number concentration
79 or size and number size distribution [11,13,17,18], but size detection limit is a major
80 shortcoming [19]. An interesting alternative is the coupling of separation techniques
81 (capillary electrophoresis, liquid chromatography or field flow fractionation (FFF)) with
82 sufficiently selective and sensitive detectors (such as inductively coupled plasma with
83 optical emission (ICP-OES) or mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) [20–22]. Among those
84 separation techniques, FFF, particularly in the asymmetric flow mode (AF4), is one of
85 the best option because it combines a high capability of separation over a wide size range
86 with a minimum sample interaction with the analytical system [14]. Moreover, the
87 coupling with ICP-MS is very advantageous because it provides simultaneous
88 information about composition, concentration, and particle size range [23–25]. This
89 combination has been used for the characterization of different inorganic NPs in food and
90 biological matrices [26–31] as well in environmental matrices [32–36]. The capabilities
91 of AF4, with either UV-visible [37] or ICP-MS [12] detection, have been initially

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92 explored for the characterization of individual PtNPs in samples of ecotoxicological and
93 biological interest [12,38] but, as far as we know, the AF4-ICP-MS online coupling has
94 not been yet used for the separation and simultaneous study of PtNPs of different sizes in
95 environmental samples.

96 Therefore, the aim of this work is to develop a new analytical methodology based on
97 AF4-ICP-MS for the separation and characterization of PtNPs in aqueous matrices.
98 Critical AF4 factors, such as cross-flow program, injection time and carrier composition
99 were optimized. The method was applied to study the behaviour of PtNPs in synthetic
100 and natural waters with different content of organic matter, as a useful strategy for
101 monitoring this type of nanoparticles in the environment.

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104 **2. Materials and methods**

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106 **2.1 Reagents**

107 All chemicals and reagents were of analytical grade. Solutions were prepared in ultrapure
108 water (18.2 M Ω cm), which was obtained from a Milli-Q[®] A10TM water purification
109 system (Millipore Corporation, USA). Commercial solutions of PtNPs (5, 30, 50, and 70
110 nm) stabilized in 2 mM citrate were purchased from nanoComposix (USA).

111 HCl (37%), methanol and NaH₂PO₄·H₂O were purchased from Scharlab (Spain). HNO₃
112 (69%) and Na₂HPO₄·12 H₂O were obtained from Merck (Germany). Rhodium (995 \pm 2
113 μ g L⁻¹) and platinum (1000 \pm 3 μ g mL⁻¹) solutions were acquired from Inorganic Ventures
114 (USA). Sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS) and sodium azide were obtained from Panreac
115 (Spain) and Acros Organics (Spain), respectively. Humic acid (HA) sodium salt (H16752,
116 molecular weight range of 2-500 kDa) was purchased from Merck (Germany).

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118 2.2 Apparatus and instrumental features

119 The AF4 system was an AF2000 (Postnova Analytics, Germany). A membrane of
120 regenerated cellulose (RC) with a molecular weight cut-off (MWCO) of 10 kDa was used
121 as the accumulation wall. The trapezoidal channel was 27.5 cm in length and from 2 to
122 0.5 cm in width, and the spacer was 350 μm thick. AF4 carrier solution was phosphate
123 buffer (1 mM, pH = 7) with the addition of SDS (0.01 %), and 2 % methanol. It was
124 filtered through 0.1 μm Teflon membrane filters (Postnova Analytics, Germany) and
125 degassed before using. All PtNPs in carrier solution and samples were filtered through
126 0.2 μm filters (Agilent Technologies, Econofilter Nylon diameter 13 mm) before injection
127 into de the AF4-ICP-MS system.

128 A Quadrupole ICP-MS Thermo X-Series (Thermo Electron Corporation, Germany)
129 equipped with a Meinhard nebulizer was employed. Rhodium ($15 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) was
130 simultaneously aspirated during the ICP-MS data acquisition and it was used to correct
131 signal drifts. The raw data of the transient isotope signal for the different PtNPs and
132 rhodium (internal standard) were further processed using the XSeries PlasmaLab
133 software. The optimum AF4-ICP-MS program is summarized in Table 1.

134 Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS) and laser Doppler velocimetry were used for obtaining
135 information on the hydrodynamic diameter and zeta potential of the particles using a
136 Malvern Zetasizer Nano ZS (Malvern Panalytical, UK). The measurements were carried
137 out using a dust-free disposable cuvette (DTS0012, Malvern Panalytical, UK) for the DLS
138 measurements and a disposable zeta cell (DTS1070, Malvern Panalytical, UK) for the
139 zeta potential measurements. For the DLS measurements, the volume was 1 mL, the
140 backscatter angle was 173° , and the temperature 25°C (after an equilibration of 2 min).

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141 Three consecutive measurements were performed using a minimum of 11 runs. The DLS
142 characteristics of the measured sample, given as Z-average, were determined by
143 averaging the replicate values ($n = 3$). For the determination of the zeta potential, 700 μL
144 of each sample were transferred to the zeta cell. After 2 min of equilibration to a
145 temperature of 25 ° C, three consecutive measurements were performed. The
146 Smoluchowski approximation was used for the calculation of the zeta potential. The mean
147 zeta potential was obtained by averaging the replicate values ($n = 3$).

148 Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) analysis were performed using a JEM 2100
149 microscope (JEOL, Japan) at 200 kV coupled with energy dispersive X-ray (EDX, INCA,
150 Oxford Instruments, UK).

151 A Milestone EthosPlus microwave oven (Milestone, USA) was used for the digestion of
152 PtNPs.

153 Total organic carbon (TOC) determination in natural water samples was carried out with
154 a CHN Analyzer Micro N/C (Analytik Jena AG, Germany).

155 Conductivity was determined in natural water samples with a Crison Micro CM 2200
156 (Crison Instruments, Spain).

157 An advanced ZX3 Vortex (Velp Scientifica, Italy) was used for the preparation of the
158 standards and samples.

159 160 2.3 Determination of concentration of PtNPs in commercial solutions

161 The concentrations of 5, 30, 50, and 70 nm PtNPs commercial solutions were estimated
162 by quantification of total Pt by ICP-MS. 10 μL of each solution was diluted in ultrapure
163 water to a volume of 5 mL, and then 250 μL of each dilution were digested with 1.5 mL

164 HCl, 0.5 mL HNO₃ and 8 mL of ultrapure water in a microwave oven. The microwave
165 heating program was: step 1) 10 min linear ramp from room temperature to 160 °C; step
166 2) 10 min linear ramp from 160 to 165 °C; step 3) cooling down to room temperature.
167 Procedural blanks were processed in each batch of digestions. Digested samples were
168 diluted with ultrapure water to a final volume of 25 mL and analysed by ICP-MS. The
169 relative signal ratio (Pt over Rh) was converted to concentration using an external
170 calibration curve (0.2 - 5 µg L⁻¹). Total platinum concentrations obtained were 53.4 ± 0.8,
171 60 ± 2, 55 ± 1, and 50 ± 5 µg mL⁻¹ (n=3) for 5, 30, 50, and 70 nm PtNPs commercial
172 solutions, respectively. Nominal concentrations provided by the manufacturer were 53,
173 54, 53 and 52 µg mL⁻¹ for 5, 30, 50, and 70 nm PtNPs, respectively.

174 2.4 Synthetic and natural water samples

176 Synthetic water samples, with (2 mg L⁻¹) or without HA, were prepared in ultrapure water
177 without any additional treatment. The two mineral waters were purchased from local
178 providers in Toledo (Spain). Dam water sample were collected from Toledo province
179 (Spain). In that case, the sampling bottle was rinsed three times with water before it was
180 filled up. Information about the characterization of the water samples is given in Table
181 S1. Mineral and dam water samples were filtered through 0.45 µm filters (Agilent
182 Technologies, Econofilter Nylon diameter 25 mm) before they were analysed.

183 All samples were spiked with commercial solutions of PtNPs at 0.106 µg mL⁻¹, 0.120 µg
184 mL⁻¹ and 0.110 µg mL⁻¹ for 5, 30, and 50 nm PtNPs, respectively, and homogenized with
185 vortex agitation. Then, they were either directly injected (0 h) or left at room temperature
186 for 48 hours and vortexed prior to injection. These experiments were carried out with
187 binary mixtures of 5 and 30 nm or 5 and 50 nm PtNPs,

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Optimization of the AF4 method

There are many experimental parameters that influence the AF4 fractionation process that should be optimized, such as carrier composition, cross flow rate and program, channel dimension, injection time, and membrane (material and pore size cut-off) [39].

The optimization was based on the fractionation of a mixture of three sizes (5, 30, and 50 nm) of PtNPs diluted in the carrier solution, vortex homogenized and filtrated (0.2 μm) before injection. The potential mass loss of this filtration process was evaluated. PtNPs were diluted in carrier individually and mixed (0.106 and 0.110 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for 5 nm and 50 nm PtNPs, respectively) and homogenized with vortex agitation during 10 s. Both filtrated (0.2 μm) and no-filtrated samples were digested as mentioned in Section 2.3 and analysed by ICP-MS. Total platinum content was determined, and recoveries were calculated, obtaining values of 95.1 ± 0.1 , 103.4 ± 0.1 and 104.1 ± 0.2 % ($n = 3$), for 5, 50 nm and a mixture of them, respectively. Therefore, problems related to losses on the filtration process can be discarded.

According to previous studies, a 350 μm thick spacer and a regenerated cellulose membrane (MWCO of 10 kDa) were selected [30,40,41]. This type of membrane has lower hydrophobicity than others, which has been reported to be beneficial for the recovery of metallic NPs [26,30]. A 50 μL injection volume was used and the PtNPs were diluted in the different tested carrier solution before injection throughout the optimization process.

Using the initial separation conditions (Program A, Table S2) and ultrapure water as carrier, the separation was not possible for this PtNP mixture (Figure S1). Considering

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212 the importance in the AF4 process, different carrier compositions were firstly studied.

213 Properties of the carrier (such as pH, ionic strength, and composition) directly influence

214 the electrostatic properties of both analyte and system [39] and the composition should

215 be chosen to simultaneously improve the operational performance and to ensure

216 compatibility with the analyte. More specifically, the addition of surfactants on the carrier

217 has proven to be beneficial in AF4 separations as they increase the analyte stability and

218 limit interactions between the analyte and the membrane [30,40]. Besides, the surfactant

219 concentration has to be optimized because it must be below the critical micelle

220 concentration for preventing undesired interference with the analyte detection [39].

221 Consequently, the presence of SDS (from 0.01 % to 0.05 % SDS) was tested. An increase

222 in relative signal intensity is observed when SDS is present, showing no relevant

223 differences for the different studied concentrations. Therefore, 0.01 % SDS was selected

224 as the optimal surfactant concentration (Figure S1).

225 Furthermore, pH and ionic strength play a critical role. In general, it is recommended to

226 use a neutral and non-reactive electrolyte system that enables pH buffering and an

227 appropriate ionic strength [39]. A phosphate buffer (1 mM) at pH = 7 (with SDS at 0.01

228 %) was tested, and a better relative signal intensity for the second fraction was observed,

229 but the separation of 30 and 50 nm PtNPs was not achieved (Figure S1).

230 A key parameter in the AF4 separation process is the elution program. Several cross-flow

231 programs (Table S2) and some modifications of them were studied. Linear (Program B,

232 Table S2) and exponential (Program C, Table S2) ramps, or even different combinations

233 of them (Program D and E, Table S2) were tested. The best results in terms of separation

234 between low and high size PtNPs were found using Program E (Figure S2).

235 Another critical parameter is injection time since it determines the analyte equilibration

236 in the carrier prior to elution [39]. Different injection times (1, 2.5, and 5 min) were tested

237 over Program E, and 2.5 min was chosen as optimum since separation between void peak
238 and 5 nm PtNPs was achieved (data not shown) (Program F, Table S2).

239 As for the study of the cross flow (V_c), according to AF4 theory, for a fixed spacer
240 thickness (w) and when V_{out} (flow rate out of the channel) remains constant (0.5 mL min^{-1}),
241 fractionation times increase with the V_c/V_{out} ratio [42]. Therefore, V_c values from
242 0.325 to 1 mL min^{-1} were tested using injection and elution steps as in Program F. Under
243 these conditions, fractionation times of all PtNPs sizes increased and the separation
244 between larger PtNPs (30 and 50 nm) was improved. Resolution between consecutive
245 peaks was calculated following Equation 1:

$$R_s = \frac{2(t_{r2} - t_{r1})}{W_1 + W_2} \quad (1)$$

247 where t_r is the retention time and W is the width of the peak.

248 Among all cross flow values tested, the best resolution (3.32) between 30 and 50 nm
249 PtNPs was obtained for 0.75 mL min^{-1} (Table S2, Program F, Figure S3), while the best
250 resolution (2.21) between void peak and 5 nm PtNPs was at 1.0 mL min^{-1} .

251 Accuracy was tested for both cross flow values by comparing the hydrodynamic
252 diameters given by the manufacturer with the ones calculated using a simplified form of
253 the FFF equation (Eq. 2) and the Stokes-Einstein equation (Eq. 3) [37]:

$$t_r = \frac{w^2}{6D} \ln \left(1 + \frac{F_c}{F_{out}} \right) \quad (2)$$

$$D = \frac{k_B T}{3\pi\eta d_H} \quad (3)$$

256 where t_r , w , D , F_c , F_{out} , k_B , T , η and d_H are fractionation time, thickness of spacer, diffusion
257 coefficient of the particles, cross flow, channel flow, Boltzman's constant, temperature

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258 (K), dynamic viscosity of fluid [0.6159 g/(m × s)] for carrier, and hydrodynamic diameter,
259 respectively.

260 The results are shown in Table 2. The manufacturer provided no data related to
261 hydrodynamic diameter of the 5 nm PtNPs, so it was not possible to assess accuracy for
262 this size. However, in the case of 30 and 50 nm PtNPs, the best agreement was achieved
263 for 0.75 mL min⁻¹, so this cross flow was chosen as optimum.

264 Finally, 2 % methanol was added to the carrier, in order to improve ionization process in
265 the ICP-MS [43]. An increment of 11 ± 3 % (n = 3) in relative signal intensity was found
266 in presence of methanol so it was also included in the carrier composition. Under these
267 final optimum elution conditions (Table 1), the separation of 5, 30, and 50 nm PtNPs was
268 achieved in less than 30 min. (Figure 1).

269 Concerning the performance of the AF4 separation method, recovery was used to assess
270 the capacity to fractionate analytes without a significant loss of material or information.
271 There are different approaches to estimate R % [39,42] in this technique and, in this work,
272 we have selected the on-line procedure. For this purpose, the sample is injected both with
273 and without the application of a cross-flow field, the peak area is integrated in each case,
274 and the difference represents the analyte loss in the system [39]. According to the
275 equations suggested by Bolea et al. [42], the membrane recovery was 100 ± 7 % (n=5)
276 for all the PtNPs studied, which is highly satisfactory under these fractionation conditions
277 (Table 1).

278 Although a general definition of a size limit of detection (LOD_{size}) is not established in
279 AF4, the molecular weight cut-off of the membrane could be settled for determining the
280 lowest size limit for sample components that are retained in the channel [44]. In our case,

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281 the molecular weight cut-off is 10 kDa, which corresponds to 1.42 nm. Therefore, the
282 theoretical LOD_{size} would be higher than this value.

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284 3.2 Application to the water samples

285 After entering aquatic environments, NPs can undergo different processes such as
286 dissolution and aggregation/agglomeration, which consequently affect to their fate,
287 bioavailability, and toxicity [17]. It is known that the behaviour of NPs depends on the
288 water chemistry and parameters like natural organic matter, ionic strength or electrolyte
289 composition can influence their fate in the environment [45,46]. In this work, the effect
290 of natural organic matter has been specifically studied, since it could play a significant
291 role over PtNPs' stability. HA will be used as a model to recreate this characteristic.

292 Firstly, the particle diameter was estimated by TEM, and the presence of Pt in all samples
293 was confirmed by EDX (Fig. S4). There was no statistically significant differences
294 ($p < 0.05$) between the found values with (4.8 ± 0.3 , 30 ± 1 , 51 ± 2 , for 5, 30, and 50 nm
295 PtNPs, respectively) and without (4.9 ± 0.2 , 30 ± 2 , 49 ± 2 , for 5, 30, and 50 nm PtNPs,
296 respectively) HA and they are in agreement with those provided by the manufacturer (4.0
297 ± 0.7 , 30 ± 3 , 46 ± 5 , for 5, 30, and 50 nm PtNPs, respectively). TEM images did not
298 show any sign of aggregation between PtNPs (Fig. S4). Moreover, aggregation process
299 of 30 and 50 nm PtNPs were studied by DLS in presence or absence of HA (2 mg L^{-1}).
300 No data are given for 5 nm PtNPs because it is below the size LOD for DLS (about 10
301 nm). Size dispersion histograms did not show the presence of any relevant fraction ($< 2\%$
302 of intensity) in the micrometre range and aggregation process can be discarded.

303 Then, the feasibility of the proposed separation method to study the behaviour of PtNPs
304 in water samples with different organic matter content was tested.

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305 In Figure 2, fractograms of synthetic water sample spiked with 5 and 30 nm PtNPs with
306 or without HA at different exposure times. At 0 h (Figure 2a), the separation of 5 and 30
307 nm PtNPs in the presence of HA showed the same profile and fractionation time as in its
308 absence. Moreover, the relative signal intensity was approximately 6 times higher in the
309 presence of HA. At 48 h of exposure (Figure 2b), the peaks disappeared in samples
310 without HA. For those containing HA, the same fractionation profile was obtained but
311 there was a decrease in the fractionation times (Figure 2b). A similar pattern was found
312 for the mixture of 5 and 50 nm PtNPs (data not shown). It is known that the high
313 complexing ability of HA can improve the stability of NPs and thus avoiding aggregation
314 or agglomeration, as reported in other studies for AgNPs [47]. Diegoli et al. [48] proposed
315 a conceptual model to explain the increased stabilization of AuNPs when humic
316 substances are present. A substitution mechanism has been demonstrated in previous
317 studies for AuNPs and AgNPs [49,50] by which humic substances can replace the small
318 coating anions and/or even overcoat them, providing a steric stabilization [48].

319 Zeta potential is used as a characterization parameter to estimate the surface charge of
320 NPs, which can be employed for understanding their physical stability [51]. In general,
321 NPs with zeta potential values greater than ± 30 mV are considered to be stable, even
322 though there are different degrees of stability [52]. The zeta potential of these PtNPs was
323 measured and more negative values were found in the presence of HA (Figure S6). The
324 reason can be the dissociation of carboxylic and phenolic groups of the HA, as previously
325 described in other works [53–55].

326 Moreover, different approaches based on the fractionation times (obtained from Figure
327 2) were used for the size characterization of PtNPs in these samples. On one hand, the
328 hydrodynamic diameters were calculated using Eqs. 2 and 3. On the other hand, a linear
329 calibration of fractionation time *versus* PtNPs ranging from 5 to 70 nm was used to

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330 estimate the modal size as previously proposed by other authors [24,42]. The linear
331 relationship between the logarithm of the fractionation ratio (described as the elution time
332 corresponding to the void peak divided by the fractionation times of the different sizes of
333 PtNPs, $\log R$) and the logarithm of the diameter in nanometres ($\log d$) of those PtNPs was
334 $\log R = -0.449 \log d + 0.1276$, $R^2 = 0.997$ (Supplementary Material, Figure S7).

335 As a result of shorter fractionation times, in presence of HA, both diameter and
336 hydrodynamic diameter decreased over time (Table 3). This can be explained by a
337 modified electrostatic interaction of the highly negatively charged PtNPs-HA complex
338 with the AF4 membrane (also negatively charged). This interaction was previously
339 reported by other authors for AgNPs and organic matter [37,56].

340 The applicability of the method was also tested in two mineral and one dam water with
341 different conductivity and TOC concentrations (Table S1). The TOC of the synthetic
342 water containing 2 mg L^{-1} of HA was also calculated to be used as a reference and it was
343 1.03 mg L^{-1} . Mixtures of 5 nm either with 30 nm or 50 nm PtNPs were used in this study.
344 When exposed to natural waters with low conductivity and TOC concentrations (Mineral
345 Water #1, Figure 3a), no significant changes were observed for either PtNPs size in
346 comparison to the synthetic water samples containing 2 mg L^{-1} of HA previously studied.
347 In samples with higher conductivity and TOC, the relative signal intensity of the 50 nm
348 PtNPs slightly increased, while that of 5 nm PtNPs disappeared (Mineral Water #2 and
349 Dam Water, Figure 3a). Similar results were obtained for the mixture of 5 nm and 30 nm
350 PtNPs (data not shown). After 48 hours of exposure no peak was observed for 5 nm PtNPs
351 in any case, whereas the relative signal intensity of 50 nm PtNPs decreased (Mineral
352 Water #1, Figure 3b) or disappeared (Mineral Water #2 and Dam Water, Figure 3b) in
353 comparison to synthetic waters. A similar behaviour was found for 5 nm & 30 nm PtNPs
354 (data not shown).

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355 These natural waters are far more complex than synthetic water samples previously used
356 in this study and give us a hint about the complexity of the transformation processes of
357 NPs that occur in real conditions. There are several factors that affect PtNPs stability,
358 such as pH, ionic strength, and the presence of cations. Further research is necessary for
359 a better understanding of the fate and behaviour of PtNPs in aqueous systems as well as
360 the role that physico-chemical parameters play in both of them. Analytical tools like the
361 one developed in the present work allow to study these changes and transformations in a
362 very useful and successful manner.

363

364 **4. Conclusions**

365 A methodology based on AF4 coupled to ICP-MS has been proposed to study and
366 characterize PtNPs. The optimization of several factors of the AF4 system was
367 fundamental to obtain reproducible results and satisfactory recoveries of NPs. V_c/V_{out}
368 ratio and carrier composition played a critical role in the optimization process. Results
369 obtained by AF4-ICP-MS show that HA greatly affects PtNPs stability over time, by
370 means of a possible interaction between organic matter and their capping agent, which
371 resulted in an increase of their stability, due to steric hindrances. This methodology was
372 also applied to study PtNPs stability in natural water samples. The methodology can be
373 useful for monitoring these types of nanoparticles in waters, as well as the possibility to
374 be expanded to other environmental matrices.

375

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598 **Legends to figures**

599

600 **Figure 1.** AF4-ICP-MS fractogram obtained for 5 ($0.106 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$), 30 ($0.120 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$),
601 and 50 ($0.110 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) nm PtNPs using phosphate buffer (1 mM) at pH = 7 with SDS
602 (0.01 %) and MeOH (2 %) as carrier and optimum operating conditions (Table 1).

603

604 **Figure 2.** Fractogram of synthetic water sample spiked with 5 ($0.106 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$), and 30
605 ($0.120 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) nm PtNPs with 2 mg L^{-1} (grey line) and without (black line) HA at
606 different exposure times: a) 0 hours, b) 48 hours. Standards without HA at 0 hours marked
607 in figure 2a are shown in figure 2b as vertical lines for a better understanding.

608

609 **Figure 3.** Fractogram of synthetic (2 mg L^{-1} of HA, dashed line) and natural water
610 samples (black, grey and light grey lines for mineral water #1, mineral water #2 and dam
611 water, respectively) spiked with 5 ($0.106 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$), and 50 ($0.110 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) nm PtNPs at
612 different exposure times: a) 0 hours, b) 48 hours.

Table 1. Optimum AF4-ICP-MS operating conditions

<i>AF4</i>			
Membrane type	Regenerated cellulose; cut-off 10 kDa		
Channel thickness	350 μm		
Injection volume	50 μL		
Carrier	Phosphate Buffer (1 mM) pH =7, SDS 0.01 %, MeOH 2 %		
Elution program	Time (min)	Regime	Cross flow (mL min^{-1})
Injection/Focusing	2.5	Injec. Flow 0.20 mL min^{-1}	0.75
Elution cross flow	16	Power (Exponent 2)	0.75 - 0.35
	10	Power (Exponent 0.5)	0.35 – 0
	2	Constant	0
<i>ICP-MS</i>			
RF-Power (KW)	1.4		
Plasma gas flow rate (L min^{-1})	15		
Carrier gas flow rate (L min^{-1})	0.98		
Nebulizer flow rate (L min^{-1})	0.9		
Auxiliary gas flow rate (L min^{-1})	1		
Spray chamber	Scott type		
Isotopes monitored	^{195}Pt , ^{103}Rh		
Dwell time (ms)	100		

Table 2. Comparison of PtNPs hydrodynamic diameter (d_h) (nm) given by the manufacturer and experimentally calculated ($n = 3$) using the FFF equation (Eq. 2) and Stokes-Einstein equation (Eq. 3) for different cross-flow values.

Nominal	Manufacturer	Calculated	
		Cross-flow (mL min ⁻¹)	
		1	0.75
5	(*)	20.9 ± 0.3	17.9 ± 0.1
30	39	44.8 ± 0.4	40.3 ± 0.3
50	61	51.3 ± 0.4	48.6 ± 0.3

(*) Not provided

Table 3. Diameters (d) and hydrodynamic diameters (d_h) of PtNPs obtained experimentally by different calculation approaches for synthetic water samples without and with HA (2 mg L^{-1}) at different times. Mean and standard deviation ($n = 3$)

Nominal size (nm)	d (nm)				d_h (nm)			
	calculated using linear regression (Fig. S7)				calculated using Eq. 2 & 3			
	Without HA		With HA		Without HA		With HA	
	0 h	48 h	0 h	48 h	0 h	48 h	0 h	48 h
5	8.1 ± 0.2	-	7.3 ± 0.4	5.0 ± 0.1	22.4 ± 0.1	-	21.6 ± 0.1	17.8 ± 0.1
30	33.5 ± 0.4	-	32.1 ± 0.5	28.0 ± 0.4	42.0 ± 0.1	-	40.8 ± 0.1	38.4 ± 0.1
50	53 ± 2	-	52.0 ± 0.2	49 ± 3	51.6 ± 0.8	-	50.8 ± 0.3	49.5 ± 0.3

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Supplementary Material

TAL-D-20-01331_Supplementary Material.docx

